

Multimetal Multiligand Complexes. Part-I. Equilibrium Study on the Formation and Stability of Mixed Ligand Mixed Metal Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper- and Zinc(II) with Aspartate and Imidazole in Aqueous Solution

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Equilibrium study on the mixed ligand and mixed metal complex formation of M^{2+} ions ($M = M^1 = M^2 = \text{Co, Ni, Cu and Zn}$) with aspartate (A^{2-}) and imidazole (B) has provided evidence of formation of homo- and heterobinuclear complexes of the types, $M_2(A)_2(B)$, $M_2(A)_2(B-H)$ and $M^1M^2(A)_2(B)$, $M^1M^2(A)_2(B-H)$ respectively, along with the usual mononuclear binary and ternary complexes, viz., $M(A)$, $M(B)$, $M(A)(B)$, $M(A)(OH)$, $M(A)(B)(OH)$. Stability constants of the complexes have been determined at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ in aqueous solution at a fixed ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3). Bridging bidentate coordination of imidazole to two metal ions using its N_1 and N_3 atoms is indicated from N_1 -H deprotonation of coordinated imidazole in the binuclear complexes at $\text{pH} > 7$.

Multimetal multiligand equilibria are very common in enzymic processes^{1,2}. Irrespective of whether a metal ion forms the integral part of the active site of an enzyme, or, the enzyme requires the metal ion as a cofactor for its activity, mixed ligand complexes involving metal ions, enzymes and the substrates are formed in most enzymic reactions. The specific role played by a metal ion in an enzymic reaction is often difficult to elucidate due to the complex nature of the protein structure. Model studies with relatively simple molecules of known structures often yield valuable information, that gives clues to the roles of metal ions in many enzymic reactions^{3,4}. The simplest model of otherwise complex natured biological metal-ligand systems may be a ternary complex, $M(A)(B)$, consisting of a metal ion, M , coordinated by two different ligands A and B , other than the solvent. Formation, structure, stability and reactivity of such ternary complexes have been exclusively studied by many workers⁵. A good amount of work in this area has also been carried out in this laboratory⁶. But mononuclear ternary complexes can not be regarded as ideal models for the metalloenzymes which have multimetal centres at their active sites. Mixed ligand mixed metal complexes involving more than one metal ions of the same, or, of different kinds may prove as better models for multimetal multiligand equilibria occurring in the biological systems. With a view to elucidate the complexation equilibria of systems involving two different metal ions and two different ligands, we describe an equilibrium study on the mixed ligand mixed metal complex formation of M^{2+} ions ($M = \text{Co, Ni, Cu and Zn}$) with aspartate (A^{2-}) and imidazole (B) in binary, ternary and quaternary systems at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ in aqueous solution at a constant ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3).

Results and Discussion

Protonated aspartic acid titrates as a triprotic acid (AH_3^+). Its pK^H values, 1.81, 3.80 and 9.59, correspond successive deprotonation of the two COOH groups and the NH_3^+ group. The dianion, A^{2-} , coordinates M^{2+} ions as a

(\bar{O}, \bar{O}, N) terdentate ligand in binary and ternary complexes using the two carboxylate oxygen atoms and the amino nitrogen atom⁷. In the presence of a strongly coordinating bidentate ligand, the A^{2-} ion may also provide (O, N) bidentate coordination to Cu^{2+} using one of the two COO^- groups and the NH_2 group to form square-planar complexes, leaving the other carboxylate group uncoordinated⁸. Protonated imidazole (BH^+) titrates as a monoprotic acid ($\text{pK}^H, 7.08$). Imidazole usually functions as a monodentate ligand, coordinating through the tertiary N_3 atom⁹.

The present work is aimed to explore the ability of imidazole to function as a (N, N) bridging bidentate ligand to form homo- and heterobinuclear complexes with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} in the presence of aspartate as the primary ligand in aqueous solution.

Complex formation in a system of two metal ions such as M^1 and M^2 and two ligands such as A and B in aqueous solution may be described¹⁰ according to equilibrium (1a),

where, the stoichiometric numbers p , q , r and s are either zero or positive intergers and t is a negative interger for a protonated species, positive interger for a hydroxo or a deprotonated species and zero for a neutral species. The overall stability constant (β_{pqrst}) of the complex, $M_p^1 M_q^2 A_r B_s (\text{OH})_t$ may be defined according to relationship (1b),

$$\beta_{\text{pqrst}} = \frac{[M_p^1 M_q^2 A_r B_s (\text{OH})_t]}{[M^1]^p [M^2]^q [A]^r [B]^s [\text{OH}]^t} \quad (1b)$$

Complex formation equilibria have been derived on the basis of the speciation curves of the complexes occurring at different pH.

(a) Binary 1 : 1 M^{2+} : A^{2-} and M^{2+} : B equilibria : The following species were considered to exist in the com-

plexation equilibria in calculating the binary stability constants, β_{10010} , β_{10200} and β_{10010} , β_{10020} , β_{01010} and β_{01020} :

Fig. 1. Speciation curves of 2 : 2 : 1 $Cu^{2+} : A^{2-} : BH^+$ system : (1) AH_3^+ , (2) AH_2 , (3) AH^- , (4) BH^+ , (5) $Cu(OH)^+$, (6) $Cu(OH)_2$, (7) $Cu(A)$, (8) $Cu(A)(OH)^-$, (9) $Cu(A)_2^{2-}$, (10) $Cu(B)^{2+}$, (11) $Cu(A)(B)$, (12) $Cu(A)(B)(OH)^-$, (13) $Cu_2(A)_2(B)$ and (14) $Cu_2(A)_2(B-H)^-$.

Formation of the hydroxo species, viz. $M(OH)^+$, $M(OH)_2$, $M(A)(OH)^-$, $M(B)(OH)^+$ etc. have been taken into consideration, as because the buffer regions corresponding to metal-ligand complex formation equilibria are found to be overlapping with the hydrolytic equilibria of the $M^{2+}(aq.)$ ions. The speciation curves (Figs. 1–3) of the systems indicate the formation of $M(A)$, $M(A)_2^{2-}$, $M(A)(OH)^-$, $M(B)^{2+}$, $M(B)_2^{2+}$ complexes with all the four

Fig. 2. Speciation curves of 2 : 2 : 1 $Zn^{2+} : A^{2-} : BH^+$ system : (1) AH_3^+ , (2) AH_2 , (3) AH^- , (4) BH^+ , (5) $Zn(OH)^+$, (6) $Zn(OH)_2$, (7) $Zn(A)$, (8) $Zn(A)(OH)^-$, (9) $Zn(A)_2^{2-}$, (10) $Zn(B)^{2+}$, (11) $Zn(A)(B)$, (12) $Zn(A)(B)(OH)^-$, (13) $Zn_2(A)_2(B)$ and (14) $Zn_2(A)_2(B-H)^-$.

M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn). The proportions of the hydroxo species, $M(OH)^+$ and $M(OH)_2$, are however found to be higher with the Zn^{2+} systems.

Fig. 3. Speciation curves of 1 : 1 : 2 : 1 $Cu^{2+} : Zn^{2+} : A^{2-} : BH$ system : (1) AH_3^+ , (2) AH_2 , (3) AH^- , (4) BH^+ , (5) $Cu(OH)^+$, (6) $Cu(OH)_2$, (7) $Zn(OH)^+$, (8) $Zn(OH)_2$, (9) $Cu(A)$, (10) $Zn(A)$, (11) $Cu(B)^{2+}$, (12) $Zn(B)^{2+}$, (13) $Cu(A)(B)$, (14) $Zn(A)(B)$, (15) $Cu_2(A)_2(B)$, (16) $Zn_2(A)_2(B)$, (17) $Cu_2(A)_2(B-H)^-$, (18) $Zn_2(A)_2(B-H)^-$, (19) $CuZn(A)_2(B)$ and (20) $CuZn(A)_2(B-H)^-$.

(b) Ternary 1 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 : 1 $M^{2+} : A^{2-} : B$ equilibria : Mixed ligand complexes, $M(A)(B)$ and $M(A)(B)(OH)^-$ are supposed to exist in the 1 : 1 : 1 $M^{2+} : A^{2-} : B$ systems, along with the binary species discussed in (a). Speciation curves (Figs. 1 and 2) indicate the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes in the pH range 3–5 according to equilibria (2) and (3),

where, $M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn . Rise in the concentrations of $M(A)(OH)^-$, $M(OH)_2$, B and A^{2-} with concomitant decline in the concentrations of the ternary $M(A)(B)$ complexes at $pH > 7$ indicates the existence of hydrolytic equilibria of the types (4) and (5),

The homobinuclear ternary complex species, $M_2(A)_2(B)$, have been considered to exist in the complexation equilibria of 2 : 2 : 1 $M^{2+} : A^{2-} : B$ systems. Speciation curves (Fig. 1) of $Cu(A)$, BH^+ and $Cu_2(A)_2(B)$ in the pH range 5.0–7.5 suggest the formation of the binuclear $Cu_2(A)_2(B)$ complex according to equilibrium (6),

Such binuclear complexes with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} , however, are found to be formed according to equilibria (7) and (8),

The aspartate ion (A^{2-}) provides (\bar{O}, \bar{O}, N) terdentate chelation to the M^{2+} ions in binary $M(A)$, $M(A_2)^{2-}$ and ternary $M(A)(B)$ complexes, where, B ligand (here, imidazole) functions as a monodentate ligand coordinating through its N_3 atom.

Simultaneous occurrence of the mononuclear ternary complexes, $M(A)(B)$, and homobinuclear ternary complexes, $M_2(A)_2(B)$ and the existence of equilibria of the type (6) suggest (N_1, N_3) bridging bidentate coordination by the imidazole (B) ligand in these binuclear complexes (1).

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(c) *Quaternary (M^1) $^{2+} : (M^2)$ $^{2+} : A : B = 1 : 1 : 2 : 1$ equilibria* : These systems are supposed to involve the heterobinuclear complexes, $M^1M^2(A)_2(B)$ in addition to the mononuclear and homobinuclear complexes discussed above. Speciation curves (Fig. 3) of the $Cu^{2+} : Zn^{2+} : 2A^{2-} : B$ system indicate the formation of the heterobinuclear complex, $CuZn(A)_2(B)$ according to equilibrium (9),

For the $Cu^{2+} : Ni^{2+} : 2A^{2-} : B$ system, an additional equilibrium (10),

is also indicated.

(d) *Deprotonation equilibria of binuclear complexes* : The homo- and the heterobinuclear complexes, $M_2(A)_2(B)$ and $M^1M^2(A)_2(B)$ respectively, show another buffer region at $pH > 7$ without the loss of either of the ligands A^{2-} or B and without any precipitation of $M(OH)_2$, $M^1(OH)_2$ or $M^2(OH)_2$. So the equilibria of the types (4) and (5) are less likely to operate in these systems. The only possible site of proton release, therefore, may be the (N_1-H) moiety of coordinated imidazole. Such metal-induced deprotonation of the coordinated imidazole ligand may be expressed according to equilibrium (11),

($M^1 = M^2 = M$ for homobinuclear complexes, $M^1 \neq M^2$ for heterobinuclear complexes).

The N_1-H deprotonation constants for homobinuclear $M(A)_2(B)$ and heterobinuclear $M^1M^2(A)_2(B)$ complexes may be defined according to relations (12) and (13) respectively,

$$K_{20210}^H = \frac{[M_2(A)_2(B-H)] [H]}{[M_2(A)_2(B)]} \quad (12)$$

$$K_{11210}^H = \frac{[M^1 M^2 (A)_2(B-H)] [H]}{[M^1 M^2 (A)_2(B)]}$$

Hence, pK_{20210}^H and pK_{11210}^H values may be calculated with the aid of relations (14) and (15) respectively,

$$pK_{20210}^H = \log \beta_{20210} - \log \beta_{20211} \quad (14)$$

$$pK_{11210}^H = \log \beta_{11210} - \log \beta_{11211} \quad (15)$$

N_1-H deprotonation constants (K_{20210}^H and K_{11210}^H) of coordinated imidazole (B) in binuclear complexes are found to be lower for the metal ions for which $M(\pi) \rightarrow B(\pi)$ bonding is stronger, as this bonding increases the electron density on the B ligand and disfavours the release of proton. Such π -bonding is, of course, absent in Zn^{II} complexes due to their tetrahedral geometry. Consequently, coordinated imidazole in the homobinuclear Zn^{II} complex, $Zn_2(A)(B)$ shows enhanced acidity. The anion, $(B-H)^-$ provides (N_1, N_3) bridging bidentate coordination (2) in the $M_2(A)_2(B-H)^-$ and $M^1M^2(A)_2(B-H)^-$ complexes.

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Imidazole residue of histidine functions as a bridging \bar{N}_1, N_3 bidentate ligand in superoxide dismutase enzyme¹¹. In the active site of bovine superoxide dismutase, one Cu^{II} ion and one Zn^{II} ion are linked by a bridging imidazolite anion of the histidine-61. The present equilibrium study

Fig. 4. Composite Irving-Williams plot of $\log \beta_{20210}$ and $\log \beta_{11210}$ values : (O) CoM, (Δ) NiM, (\square) CuM and (\bullet) ZnM (where $M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn).

thus provides an evidence of formation of imidazole bridged homo- and heterobinuclear complex species in aqueous solution.

Stability constants of the binary M(A), M(B) and ternary M(A)(B) complexes (Table 1) fall in the Irving-Williams order¹² : $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$. Overall stability

Fig. 5. Composite Irving-Williams plot of $\log \beta_{20211}$ and $\log \beta_{11211}$ values : (O) CoM, (Δ) NiM (\square) CuM and (\bullet) ZnM (where M = Co, Ni, Cu and Zn).

constants, β_{20210} , β_{11210} (Fig. 4) and β_{20211} and β_{11211} (Fig. 5) of the binuclear complexes form a composite Irving-Williams order, if one of the two metal ions is kept fixed and the other is varied in the sequence : $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ and Zn^{II} . Stability of binuclear complexes are found to be in the order : $\text{CuCu} > \text{CuNi} > \text{CuCo} > \text{CuZn} > \text{NiZn} > \text{NiNi} > \text{CoNi} > \text{CoZn} > \text{ZnZn} > \text{CoCo}$. Slightly higher stability of the Zn^{II} complexes over the corresponding Co^{II} complexes may be due to slightly higher softness of the Zn^{II} ion relative to Co^{II} with regard to their binding to the imidazole (B) ligand. Similar order of stability constants has also been observed with the binary M^{2+} /imidazole and ternary M^{2+} /NTA/imidazole and M^{2+} /EDTA/imidazole systems⁹. Moreover, profound tendency of $\text{Co}^{2+}(d^7)$ ion to form tetrahedral complexes¹³ may also be responsible for slightly lower values of binding constants of the Co^{II} complexes. The single $\text{Ni}(\pi) \rightarrow \text{B}(\pi)$ back-bonding in $\text{NiZn}(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$ complex adds to the stability of this complex, whereas two opposing $\text{Ni}(\pi) \rightarrow \text{B}(\pi)$ bondings in $\text{Ni}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$ complex possibly mutually weaken each other by increasing the electron density on the B ligand. As a result, the stability of the Ni-Ni complex is slightly lower than that of the Ni-Zn complex. Binuclear complexes with higher value of overall stability constant (β_{20210} or β_{11210}) show higher acidity of $\text{N}_1\text{-H}$ proton of the bridging imidazole ligand (Table 1) due to $\text{B}(\sigma) \rightarrow \text{M}(\sigma)$ bonding.

TABLE 1-PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND BINARY, TERNARY AND QUATERNARY CONSTANTS ($\log \beta_{\text{pqrst}}$)^{*} IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

Temp = $25 \pm 1^\circ$, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3)

[A = aspartate²⁻; B = imidazole]

(a) Proton-ligand constants ($\log \beta_{00rst}$)

	p	q	r	s	t	
AH_3^+	0	0	1	0	-3	15.20
AH_2	0	0	1	0	-2	13.89
AH^-	0	0	1	0	-1	9.59
BH^+	0	0	0	1	-1	7.08

(b) Metal-ligand constants ($\log \beta_{10rst}$) : Binary systems

		Co	Ni	Cu	Zn
$\text{M}(\text{OH})^+$	1 0 0 0 1	-8.23	-8.10	-6.29	-7.89
$\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$	1 0 0 0 2	-17.83	-16.87	-13.10	-14.92
$\text{M}(\text{A})$	1 0 1 0 0	5.90	7.33	8.94	5.69
$\text{M}(\text{A})_2^{2-}$	1 0 2 0 0	9.82	12.00	15.83	9.77
$\text{M}(\text{A})(\text{OH})^-$	1 0 1 0 1	-3.33	-1.77	1.23	-3.20
$\text{M}(\text{B})^{2+}$	1 0 0 1 0	2.70	3.69	4.33	2.97

(c) Metal-ligand constants ($\log \beta_{\text{pqrst}}$) : Ternary systems

		Co-Co	Ni-Ni	Cu-Cu	Zn-Zn
$\text{M}(\text{A})(\text{B})$	1 0 1 1 0	8.68	11.08	13.00	9.88
$\text{M}(\text{A})(\text{B})(\text{OH})$	1 0 1 1 1	-1.33	-1.44	4.52	-2.90
$\text{M}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$	2 0 2 1 0	18.08	21.06	24.83	18.73
$\text{M}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B-H})^-$	2 0 2 1 1	10.28 (8.80)	15.08 (5.98)	18.92 (5.91)	12.18 (6.55)

(d) Metal-ligand constants ($\log \beta_{\text{pqrst}}$) : Quaternary systems

		Co-Ni	Co-Cu	Co-Zn
$\text{M}^1\text{M}^2(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$	1 1 2 1 0	20.48	23.76	18.88
$\text{M}^1\text{M}^2(\text{A})_2(\text{B-H})^-$	1 1 2 1 1	12.68 (7.80)	16.10 (7.66)	11.48 (7.40)
$\text{M}^1\text{M}^2(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$	1 1 2 1 0	24.15	21.45	22.94
$\text{M}^1\text{M}^2(\text{A})_2(\text{B-H})^-$	1 1 2 1 1	17.00 (7.15)	13.88 (7.57)	15.80 (7.14)

$\text{p}K_{20210}^{\text{H}}$ and $\text{p}K_{11210}^{\text{H}}$ values are shown in the parenthesis.

*Limits of error : ± 0.02 in log scale.

(e) Electronic spectra of metal-ligand mixtures : The formation of binuclear complexes, $\text{Cu}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$, $\text{CuZn}(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$ and their deprotonated forms, $\text{Cu}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B-H})^-$ and $\text{CuZn}(\text{A})_2(\text{B-H})^-$ is also evident from the superimposed electronic spectral curves (Fig. 6) of the binary 1 : 2 Cu^{2+} : A^{2-} and Cu^{2+} : B, ternary 1 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 : 1 Cu^{2+} : A^{2-} :

TABLE 2-ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF BINARY, TERNARY AND QUATERNARY METAL-LIGAND MIXTURES IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

Temp = $25 \pm 1^\circ$, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3)

Composition	pH	Complex	λ_{max} (nm)
-	5.00	$\text{Cu}(\text{aq})^{2+}$	805
$\text{Cu}^{2+}:\text{AH}_2$	(1:2)	$\text{Cu}(\text{A})_2^{2-}$	678
$\text{Cu}^{2+}:\text{BH}^+$	(1:2)	$\text{Cu}(\text{B})_2^{2+}$	660
$\text{Cu}^{2+}:\text{AH}_2:\text{BH}^+$	(1:1:1)	$\text{Cu}(\text{A})(\text{B})$	669
$\text{Cu}^{2+}:\text{AH}_2:\text{BH}^+$	(2:2:1)	$\text{Cu}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$	690
$\text{Cu}^{2+}:\text{AH}_2:\text{BH}^+$	(2:2:1)	$\text{Cu}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B-H})^-$	666
$\text{Cu}^{2+}:\text{Zn}^{2+}:\text{AH}_2:\text{BH}^+$	(1:1:2:1)	$\text{CuZn}(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$	641
$\text{Cu}^{2+}:\text{Zn}^{2+}:\text{AH}_2:\text{BH}^+$	(1:1:2:1)	$\text{CuZn}(\text{A})_2(\text{B-H})^-$	630
$\text{Cu}^{2+}:\text{Zn}^{2+}:\text{AH}_2:\text{BH}^+$	(1:1:2:2)	$\text{Cu}(\text{A})(\text{B}) + \text{Zn}(\text{A})(\text{B})$	644

B and quaternary 1 : 1 : 2 : 1 $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{Zn}^{2+} : \text{A}^{2-} : \text{B}$ mixtures at pH values corresponding to concentration maxima of the $\text{Cu}(\text{A})_2^{2-}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{B})_2^{2+}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{A})(\text{B})$, $\text{Cu}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$, $\text{Cu}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B}-\text{H})^-$, $\text{CuZn}(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$ and $\text{CuZn}(\text{A})_2(\text{B}-\text{H})^-$ complexes under the same experimental condition. As expected, the λ_{max} value (Table 2) of the ternary $\text{Cu}(\text{A})(\text{B})$ complex (669 nm) is found to be intermediate between the λ_{max} values of the two binary complexes, $\text{Cu}(\text{A})_2^{2-}$ (678 nm) and $\text{Cu}(\text{B})_2^{2+}$ (660 nm). The binuclear complex, $\text{Cu}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$ shows λ_{max} at a

Fig. 6. Spectral curves of binary, ternary and quaternary metal-ligand mixtures : (1) $\text{Cu}(\text{A})(\text{B})$, (2) $\text{Cu}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$, (3) $\text{Cu}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B}-\text{H})^-$, (4) $\text{CuZn}(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$, (5) $\text{CuZn}(\text{A})_2(\text{B}-\text{H})^-$, (6) $\text{Cu}(\text{A})(\text{B}) + \text{Zn}(\text{A})(\text{B})$, (7) $\text{Zn}(\text{A})(\text{B})$ and (8) $\text{Cu}^{2+}(\text{aq})$.

longer wavelength (684 nm) than the mononuclear ternary complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{A})(\text{B})$, as the average ligand field exerted by the bridging imidazole ligand (B) on two Cu^{II} ions in the binuclear $\text{Cu}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$ complex is definitely lower than the field exerted by the same (B) ligand when it coordinates one Cu^{II} ion as a monodentate ligand in the ternary $\text{Cu}(\text{A})(\text{B})$ complex.

$\text{N}_1\text{-H}$ deprotonation of the bridging imidazole (B) ligand in binuclear $\text{Cu}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$ and $\text{CuZn}(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$ complexes puts an additional electron on the bridging imidazole. The resulting anion, $(\text{B}-\text{H})^-$ obviously exerts a stronger ligand field than the neutral B ligand. As a result, the binuclear complexes, $\text{Cu}_2(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$ and $\text{CuZn}(\text{A})_2(\text{B})$ undergo blue-shifts in their absorption maxima by 15–20 nm on raising the pH of the solution above 7.5. This provides further support to the validity of the proposition of the deprotonation equilibria (11).

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO_2 -free water. Metal nitrate solutions were standardized by complexometric EDTA titration method combined with ion-exchange and acid-base titrations¹⁴.

pH measurements were made with a Systronics 335 pH

meter using a special glass electrode (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ (thermostated).

Metal-ligand mixtures of following compositions were prepared for pH-metric titrations : (i) $\text{M}^{2+} : \text{ligand} (\text{AH}_3^+ \text{ or } \text{BH}^+) = 1 : 1, 1 : 2 \text{ and } 1 : 5$ binary mixtures, (ii) $\text{M}^{2+} : \text{AH}_3^+ : \text{BH}^+ = 1 : 1 : 1 \text{ and } 2 : 2 : 1$ ternary mixture⁸ and (iii) $(\text{M}^1)^{2+} : (\text{M}^2)^{2+} : \text{AH}_3^+ : \text{BH}^+ = 1 : 1 : 2 : 1$ quaternary mixtures, where, M, M^1 and M^2 are Co, Ni, Cu and Zn as the case may be. Ionic strength (*I*) of all the solutions were maintained constant, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3), by adding required amounts of NaNO_3 . Procedure for pH-metric titration was the same as described elsewhere⁶.

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants were calculated with the aid of SCOGS computer programme¹⁰. Preliminary estimates of some of the binary constants supplied to the computer as input data were made according to the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹⁵ using the pH-titration curves. Computer refined values of the constants corresponding to minimum standard deviation (± 0.01 ml in the titre) were accepted and used for the calculation of the speciation curves. Complexation equilibria were elucidated by analysing these speciation curves obtained as computer outputs. Spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Hitachi-U3501 spectrophotometer.

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